

Looking forward to $B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ and $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$

Maria Domenica Galati ^{3,5}

¹Physics Department, University of Lancaster, Lancaster, United Kingdom

²Van Swinderen Institute, University of Groningen, Groningen, the Netherlands

³Nikhef National Institute for Subatomic Physics, Amsterdam, the Netherlands

⁴Fakultät Physik, Technische Universität Dortmund, Dortmund, Germany

⁵Gravitational Waves and Fundamental Physics, Maastricht University, Maastricht, the Netherlands

Abstract

These proceedings present the outcome of a feasibility study using RapidSim simulation software that demonstrates that the LHCb experiment will be capable of observing the decays $B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ and $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ using the data that is being collecting during Run 3 of the LHC. The proposed analysis exploits the small distance of only 5.1 millimetres between the sensing elements of LHCb's innermost silicon pixel detector, the VELO, and the LHC's proton beams to identify direct pixel hits in the VELO that can be associated with the charged B^+ , B_c^+ or τ^+ particles. By using this extra information, the limitations due to the missing momentum and vertex information will be significantly reduced. This provides enough statistical power to pursue the measurements of these two decay channels at the LHC. In particular for the decay $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$, which has been identified by the high energy physics community as a key objective for experiments at the planned next-generation particle accelerators, this means we do not need to wait for the 2030s or beyond to get first experimental constraints.

1 Introduction

The purely leptonic $B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ and $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ decays are sensitive probes to physics Beyond the Standard Model (BSM) [1], with their SM branching fractions predicted to be [2, 3]:

$$\mathcal{BR}(B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau)|_{\text{SM}} = (0.869_{-0.030}^{+0.031}) \times 10^{-4}; \quad (1)$$

$$\mathcal{BR}(B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau)|_{\text{SM}} = (1.95 \pm 0.09) \times 10^{-2}. \quad (2)$$

The experimental world average¹ of $\mathcal{BR}(B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau)$, compiled by the Particle Data Group [5], is

$$\mathcal{BR}(B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau) = (1.09 \pm 0.24) \times 10^{-4}, \quad (3)$$

which is compatible with the Standard Model prediction, but no discovery has been claimed yet. In contrast, the decay $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ has not yet been experimentally measured. Its first determination is widely recognised as a key milestone in flavour physics and it has been listed among the physics goals of several proposed future facilities, including the Future Circular Collider (FCC) [3, 6–8] and the Circular Electron Positron Collider (CEPC) [9].

The interest in $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ is further strengthened by the long-standing anomalies observed in the ratios

$$R(D^{(*)}) = \frac{\mathcal{BR}(B^0 \rightarrow D^{(*)-} \tau^+ \nu_\tau)}{\mathcal{BR}(B^0 \rightarrow D^{(*)-} \ell^+ \nu_\ell)}, \quad \ell \in \{e, \mu\}, \quad (4)$$

*Presenting author.

¹Note that this average does not yet include the recent measurement from the Belle II collaboration [4].

which compare the rates of semileptonic B decays involving a τ lepton to those involving lighter charged leptons. The current global average of $R(D^{(*)})$ measurements from BaBar, Belle, LHCb and Belle II exhibits a combined tension of about 3.8σ with respect to the SM expectation [10].

As it can be seen by comparing the SM Feynman diagrams in Figure 1, the $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ decay proceeds via the same $b \rightarrow c \tau \nu$ quark-level transition that also governs $B^0 \rightarrow D^{(*)-} \tau^+ \nu_\tau$, and therefore provides valuable complementary information about the underlying physics processes [11–13].

Figure 1: Leading-order Feynman diagrams for the purely leptonic decay $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ (left) and the semileptonic decay $B^0 \rightarrow D^{(*)-} \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ (right).

Observing the decays $B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ and $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ at a hadron collider is considered to be difficult. Because both the $B_{(c)}$ and the subsequent τ decay produce neutrinos, key kinematic information is lost. In the busy environment of proton–proton collisions, this makes it challenging to distinguish signal from backgrounds.

The proposed strategy at LHCb is to look for evidence of a charged particle that travelled between the primary vertex (PV) created by the proton–proton collision and the decay vertex of the τ lepton (TV) [14]. The latter can be reconstructed for $\tau^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- \pi^+ \bar{\nu}_\tau$ decays, which is the final state considered in this feasibility study.

Both the $B_{(c)}$ meson and the τ lepton are charged, have lifetimes of the order of 1 ps, and therefore travel distances of the order of a centimetre at LHC energies. Given that the silicon sensors of the upgraded LHCb VELO are positioned as close as 5.1 mm from the LHC beams [15,16], there is a non-negligible probability that the $B_{(c)}$ or the τ traverse a sensor before decaying. This leaves a measurable signal in the VELO, which will be referred to as *VELO-hit* (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of a $B_{(c)}^+$ meson decaying to a τ^+ lepton, which subsequently decays to three pions. The gray vertical lines represent the VELO sensor modules, with red crosses indicating hits between PV and TV. The dashed lines represent neutrinos, which are not detected in the LHCb experiment.

Selecting events containing at least one VELO-hit places strong constraints on the minimum flight distance between the PV and the TV. Furthermore, the location of the VELO-hit closest to the PV provides a more accurate estimate of the initial flight direction of the B meson than the line connecting the PV and the reconstructed τ vertex. This improved directional information enhances the kinematic reconstruction of the event and strengthens the separation of signal from background.

2 Data simulation

The feasibility study is based on RapidSim [17,18], a tool designed for fast simulations of heavy-flavour hadron decays. RapidSim provides the kinematics of the decays of interest, but does not model proton–proton collisions or interactions with the detectors.

Background events with a similar experimental signature to that of $B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ and $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$, i.e. three charged pions originating from a common displaced vertex, can originate from charm- and beauty-hadron decays. We include the following three background cocktails, matching the list of decay channels used in the feasibility study for FCC-ee [3]:

- $D \rightarrow \tau \nu$, consisting of $D^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ and $D_s^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$;
- $B \rightarrow D 3\pi$, consisting of $B_h \rightarrow D_h \pi^+ \pi^+ \pi^-$ and $B_h \rightarrow D_h^* \pi^+ \pi^+ \pi^-$;
- $B \rightarrow DY$, consisting of $B_h \rightarrow D_h \tau^+ \nu_\tau$, $B_h \rightarrow D_h^* \tau^+ \nu_\tau$, $B_h \rightarrow D_h D_s^+$, $B_h \rightarrow D_h^* D_s^+$ and $B_h \rightarrow D_h^* D_s^{*+}$.

Here, B_h denotes any of $\{B^+, B_d^0, B_s^0, \Lambda_b^0\}$, with the corresponding D_h being one of $\{\bar{D}^0, D^-, D_s^-, \Lambda_c^-\}$. The intermediate decays $D_s^{*+} \rightarrow D_s^+ \gamma$, $D_s^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$, and $\tau^+ \rightarrow \pi^+ \pi^- \pi^+ \bar{\nu}_\tau$, are implicitly assumed. In this study, D_h is assumed to not contribute to the reconstructed final-state particles and it is therefore ignored within RapidSim.

Signal and background events are first filtered based on the geometric acceptance of the LHCb detector and the application of the following selection cuts:

- the invariant mass of the two combinations of oppositely charged pions, $m_{\pi^+ \pi^-}$, satisfies $m_{\pi^+ \pi^-} \leq 1670$ MeV, which roughly corresponds to $m_{\pi^+ \pi^-} \leq m_\tau - m_\pi$;
- the invariant mass of the three pions, $m_{3\pi}$, satisfies 500 MeV $\leq m_{3\pi} \leq 1800$ MeV;
- the transverse momentum of the three pion system exceeds 5 GeV;
- at least one VELO-hit is present between the PV and TV, confirming the existence of a charged intermediate particle.

A factor ε_{iso} is applied to the event yields of $B \rightarrow D3\pi$ and $B \rightarrow DY$ decays, where additional detectable particles beyond the three signal pions are present. ε_{iso} represents the probability that all these additional particles escape reconstruction, causing the background event to mimic the three-pion signal topology. A conservative value of $\varepsilon_{\text{iso}} = 10\%$ is chosen based on both performance numbers from existing tools at LHCb [19] and reconstruction efficiencies of both charged and neutral particles [20–23].

The expected number of events is calculated by combining the relevant production cross sections, the branching fractions of the decays, and the integrated luminosity of the dataset, weighted for an efficiency factor combining the geometric acceptance of the detector, the applied selection cuts, and the probability that additional particles escape reconstruction.

3 Sensitivity study

A sensitivity study is performed to determine the feasibility of observing the $B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ and $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ decays at the LHCb experiment using the data collected during Run 3 of the LHC. The study is based on 2000 pseudo-experiments, in which the signal yields are extracted from an extended two-dimensional binned maximum-likelihood fit to toy datasets. The two fitted observables are the *corrected mass* and the output of a boosted decision tree (BDT) classifier.

The corrected mass is defined as

$$m_{corr} = \sqrt{m_{3\pi}^2 + |\vec{p}_{3\pi}^\perp|^2} + |\vec{p}_{3\pi}^\perp|, \quad (5)$$

where $\vec{p}_{3\pi}^\perp$ is the momentum of the three-pion system transverse to the B -meson flight direction, approximated by the line connecting the PV to the first VELO-hit.

The BDT is trained to discriminate $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ signal from background using the distributions of the three-pion kinematic and topological observables, including momentum, impact parameter, flight distance, and invariant mass.

Figure 3: Distributions of m_{corr} (left) and the BDT classifier output (right), showing the projections of the two-dimensional fit on a representative pseudo-dataset generated with an integrated luminosity of 10 fb^{-1} .

In the fit, the template shapes of all five components ($B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$, $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$, $B \rightarrow D 3\pi$, $B \rightarrow D Y$ and $D \rightarrow \tau \nu$) are fixed, with the event yields being the only free parameters.

The projections of a representative fit performed with an integrated luminosity of 10 fb^{-1} onto m_{corr} and the BDT score are shown in Figure 3. The fit procedure is repeated for several luminosity scenarios. For each scenario, the mean relative uncertainty on the fitted $B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ and $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ yields is defined as the average, over the 2000 pseudo-experiments, of the ratio $\sigma_{\text{fit}}/n_{\text{fit}}$, where n_{fit} is the fitted yield and σ_{fit} its associated uncertainty. The resulting relative uncertainties are plotted in Figure 4 as a function of the integrated luminosity. The figure also illustrates the impact of different levels of systematic uncertainty, each expressed as a fraction of the statistical uncertainty, on the overall precision of the measurement.

4 Results and conclusions

Based on the presented feasibility study, the observation of the $B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ and $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ decays at the LHCb experiment appears to be within reach using data from LHC Run 3.

Considering only statistical uncertainties, the $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ decay can be observed with a data sample corresponding to an integrated luminosity slightly above 10 fb^{-1} . When including

Figure 4: Mean relative precision on the fitted $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ (left) and $B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ (right) yields as a function of integrated luminosity, based on 2000 pseudo-experiments per point. Different curves correspond to scenarios where the systematic uncertainty is assumed to be 0, 25%, 50%, or 100% of the statistical uncertainty. These scenarios are included to illustrate the impact of potential systematic effects not explicitly evaluated in this study. For the $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ decay, the dashed red line indicates the 3σ significance level threshold, while the solid red line corresponds to 5σ .

a systematic uncertainty of the same size as the statistical uncertainty, a dataset of slightly more than 20 fb^{-1} would be required to claim the first observation. Given the luminosity already collected by LHCb since 2024 [24], such a dataset is expected to be available by mid-2026.

For the $B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ decay, a relative precision smaller than 5% is obtained for all considered luminosity scenarios, indicating that the observation of this decay is already feasible with the data collected to date.

These results demonstrate that LHCb has the potential to provide the first experimental constraints on $B_c^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$ and a precise measurement of $B^+ \rightarrow \tau^+ \nu_\tau$, offering complementary information to the ongoing tests of lepton flavour universality in $R(D^{(*)})$ and the search for physics beyond the Standard Model.

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